

Impact of Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement of University Students: Case Study Erbil City

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Abstract:- This study emphasizes the role of higher education in preparing students to acquire knowledge and vocational and cognitive skills to enter society and serve their community. The motivation behind this paper is to evaluate the effect of socioeconomic status on the academic achievement of university students in city Erbil. Factors that lead to students' academic achievement are essential to identify. The objective of this study was to investigate the relationship among socioeconomic status and academic accomplishments among university students in Erbil city. The survey was used to generate baseline data from a randomly assigned sample of 230 university student in 2022 through random sampling. Enlightenment measurements, data were analyses utilize chi-square (χ^2) test and iterative binary logistic regression using SPSS program investigation. The results indicated that there are many factors to improve the academic achievement of university students. In addition, some factors, such as good relationships between teachers and students, have a great impact on students' academic achievement, as do providing all necessary equipment for students and providing job opportunities for students. Graduate this will encourage students to achieve high academic standards.

Keywords:- Socioeconomic; status, academic; achievement; university students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Socioeconomics is a way of describing people based on their education, income, and type of job. Socioeconomic status is usually described as low, medium and high. People with lower socioeconomic status usually have more or less access to financial, educational, social, and health resources than people with higher socioeconomic status. The socioeconomic status of the community has an impact on the achievements of the community and on the basis of family income, which helps students to meet all their needs and improve their educational level. Also, the analysing a family's socio-economic status, parental education and occupation are examined, as well as combined income, versus an individual, when their own attributes are assessed [1]. In this study, the researchers investigated the factors that affect student performance and achievement, which depend on the different socio-economic statuses in society, and how socio-economic status affects students' academic achievement. This also depends on how different levels of

socio-economic status in the community affect students' progress. The researcher also highlights the literature on how parents' livelihoods affect their students' progress in school and their ability to achieve high grades in their classes. The study also presents the impact of income and occupation on students' educational level. The study determines the impact of many socioeconomic indicators on student achievement performance. In addition, surveys on education and higher education to test students' learning achievement analyze which factors of the educational environment and socioeconomic status have the greatest impact on student achievement. Identifying such factors and assessing their impact is important in order to control variation in student achievement [2]. Poverty is a way of life that affects the whole lives of individuals and the world. For many years, policymakers, educators, economists, researchers, and concerned citizens around the world have joined efforts to solve this complex and widespread problem in society. Most researchers and scientists acknowledge that it is very difficult to ignore such a big issue, and the efforts of researchers to solve poverty so that individuals in society can improve in all aspects and improve the socio-economic situation of society have a positive impact on student performance. If the socio-economic situation of the community is poor, it has a negative impact on students' academic progress [3]. In addition, the status of education is linked to the socio-economic status of the individual. If the socio-economic status of an individual is poor, there will be a huge gap in the education sector, and this will have a huge impact on the academic performance of students [4]. and in a healthy educational environment that focuses on accountability based on standard principles for the learning of students in subgroups. In order for the education system to be on track, it must be aware of all the problems that poor students face and be ready to implement programs and initiatives to combat the problems that prevent students from studying in education universities so that every individual in society has access to improving their academic performance [5]. Furthermore, for a long time, socioeconomic status was not considered to affect students' academic performance. However, it was later found that family socioeconomic status had a significant impact on work performance, welfare, and educational attainment. Various fields of education, sociology, and psychology attracted the attention of researchers, who conducted many studies to find the relationship among socioeconomic and students' academic accomplishment [6]. The socioeconomic status of an individual is also a measure of that person's socioeconomic

status. Socioeconomic status is also positively associated with improved living conditions for individuals, improved health status. Socioeconomic status is also a way of describing people based on their education, income, and type of work. Socioeconomic status is usually described as low, medium, and high. People with higher or lower socioeconomic status have less access to financial, educational, social and health resources than those with higher socioeconomic status [7]. Socioeconomic status is a combined economic and sociological aggregate measure of a person's work experience and an individual's or family's socioeconomic status relative to others, based on income, education, and occupation. Families with high socioeconomic status are more successful because they can provide their children with all the necessities to achieve all their desires. Students with high socioeconomic status also typically have access to a wide range of resources to promote and support their children's development [8]. Also, families with high socio-economic status can provide all the necessities for their families and children, and their students' academic performance is much better than that of families with very low socio-economic status and low-income or unemployed parents. Their livelihoods are poor because they cannot provide for all their needs and those of their families and children, which has a huge impact on the level of their education [9]. The researcher focuses on the impact of socio-economic status on students' academic achievement, as well as to treat and control many other factors [10]. Socioeconomic status has been defined in many different ways by researchers, and it also determines the economic status of people in society and their role in society [11]. Such research helps to accurately identify the phenomena in the community among other members of the community to determine the economic status and livelihood capacity of the so-called socioeconomic status as mentioned above. Also, by calculating the list of facilities and luxuries that people possess, we see that they are all produced in the field of socio-economic status. While some people focus on the maintenance of their social status or rank in society, others counter the facilities. There are many factors that affect the understanding of socio-economic status, including the way individuals in society or parents raise their children, and family size affects socio-economic status [12]. Students with high socioeconomic status are more likely to progress academically. Also, people with low or middle socioeconomic status have less access to resources and facilities, so these people remain at a low level and are less likely to succeed. Therefore, socio-economic status is important for the development of society [11]. Also, the impact of various including a student's home socioeconomic environment, educational environmental factors, on learning achievement includes analyzes of all international surveys on education Not so well at home. In addition, assessing the impact of students' home socio-economic factors on student accomplishment is important for a more accurate assessment of the added value of schools in order to achieve higher accomplishment [13]. Furthermore, it showed that the socio-economic status of students' families serves as a bridge between their children and society, and children's socio-economic status determines that if families do not serve their children well or properly, their children will not succeed

Their fathers should be rich and educated [14]. Much effort has been made to identify the relationship between socioeconomic status and academic achievement performance through many sociological and educational works, these socioeconomic studies empirical studies investigating this relationship have accumulated steadily over the past few years. What has also emerged from extensive reviews and from empirical studies of the literature is that there is a significant relationship between socioeconomic status and academic achievement performance [15]. A family's socio-economic status and education determine the quality of a student's academic achievement. In general, children with high or middle socioeconomic parents are better off learning early because they have created a favorable environment for their children to have access to all learning materials at home because of their facilities [16]. There are many factors that affect student achievement. Students' academic performance is determined by where they live, age, gender, parents' socio-economic status, parents' income, the school environment, and their individual status in society. Family status also has a significant impact on students' academic achievement and success. On the other hand, socio-economic status includes education, economic status, social, and cultural aspects that are used for the maturity and development of the family [17]. It was also found that students from the high socioeconomic status group achieved significantly more than students from the middle or low socioeconomic status group, revealing a positive relationship between socioeconomic status and achievement in different subjects. As well, no evidence of differential significance was revealed between boys and girls regarding their academic achievement [18]. The results of these studies showed that a student with high socioeconomic had a significant effect on student grades and academic performance, much better than a student with poor or low socioeconomic status, indicating that socioeconomic status is very important for students in every way [19]. Students' socioeconomic status and academic achievement are strongly related due to the complex interaction of a number of variables. In general, socioeconomic status significantly influences learners' learning and teaching experiences [20]. investigated the effects of socioeconomic status on student performance. The results showed that socio-economic status, education, occupation, and parental facilities at home affect student achievement [21].

A. *The Purpose of the Study*

To determine the effect of parents' socioeconomic status on university students' achievement as well as the effect of students' parents' educational level on university students' academic achievement. to identify the effect of parental occupation on the academic achievement of university students.

B. *The Problem of the Study*

This study will benefit teachers according to the information needed, the approach of all students, and how to behave and deal with students integrating teaching units. Finding the generations of this research for students to identify their problems and how to overcome them this survey of students in Erbil does not provide much insight about the dominance of socioeconomic outcomes on student

achievement. Economic resources are limited in Erbil. Considering ideas and insights for us, whether the social-ready home learning environment of university students affects the achievements of students in Erbil, and frequently the results of questions in other much richer and better planned. In addition, it is important to know which aspects of the entire home environment have a weaker or other impact on university students' achievement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[2], this study investigated the impact of socioeconomic status on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Delhi, India. The study was conducted in 15 public and private schools in Delhi. Also used statistical tests such as the F-Test, T-test, as well as used multiple linear regression for analyze the data. Also, after conducting the data analysis, we came to the conclusion that there was a difference between families with high social status and families with low social status. It has also become increasingly clear from this study that gender affects academic achievement at the secondary school level. Academic achievement was also found to be influenced by socioeconomic status, with those belonging to high and medium socioeconomic status showing better performance. Based on these findings, some recommendations with great implications for both practice and further research were provided.

[22], investigated the factors affecting the socioeconomic status of families on academic achievement of students' performance at secondary level in Allama Iqbal Town, Pakistan. The data was collected through a questionnaire. The information review examiner was utilized to choose an example of 171 students. The investigation utilized the t-test to dissect information. The indicated, it was concluded that parents' financial status, financial and moral support, and socioeconomic status affect student academic achievement, the provision of a learning environment at home, and the incentives provided by parents to motivate the children to work harder and achieve higher. As it was found that parents' source of income is a vital factor that effects the academic achievement of students, as a result, it is suggested that the government provide incentives to students as well as assistance to low-income families. Free books supplemented by stationeries and scholarships are recommended, which have the capacity to boost the performance of the students academically.

[23], In this study, the researcher felt the need to investigate the effects of socioeconomic status and gender on the accomplishment performance of secondary school students. To analyze and evaluate the data obtained in this study, the researcher used ANOVA and T test and used SPSS program. In addition, for data collection, 200 middle school students were randomly recruited from schools: 99 girls and 101 boys. The data of the study was randomly collected from four government schools in Lahore. The outcomes indicated that students with good socioeconomic status scored high and students with low socioeconomic status scored low, and no differences were detected on the basis of gender or student grade. These studies suggest the

state should help poor students or improve the school environment to help poor students continue their education and improve their academic performance.

[17], analyzed the impact of socioeconomic status on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in India. The researcher used a survey method for this study recruited 170 students from four different secondary schools. Also used to investigate Pearsons' correlation coefficient and t-test, analyzed the data with SPSS. The findings of the study showed that there is positive correlation exist between socioeconomic status and academic achievement of senior secondary school students, it also highlights that significance difference is present among different socioeconomic status group in their academic achievement. It further revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female students in their academic achievement.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted among university students in Erbil. Erbil is located between, Duhok, Mosul, Kirkuk and Sulaymaniyah; It is located on the border between Iran and Turkey. Duhok is also located on the Turkish-Syrian border. Duhok is close to Mosul and Erbil. Sulaymaniyah is close to Erbil and Kirkuk, located on the Iranian border. In addition, a questionnaire was prepared to obtain and collect the necessary data for the study on university students in Erbil city during 2022 the data were collected. The data collected by the research instrument were analyzed according to each research question and hypothesis. Descriptive statistics (such frequencies and as percentages) were used to answer the research questions. In addition, a Chi square (χ^2) was conducted to calculate variance within each group for factors in two groups. Also Chi square is a statistical technique that evaluates potential differences in an among categorical level dependent variables with a nominal-level variable logistic regression analysis was used allowing inclusion of any preferred variable. The Chi-Square test is a statistical procedure used by researchers to examine the differences between categorical variables in the same population.

The binary logistic regression model was used in this investigation. The logistic regression model indicates how a set of independent cause and a categorical answers variable are linked. As a result, the logistic regression model was utilized in the statistical section of the study since it can be used to determine the relationship between the likelihood of the severity of the effect socio economy on performance student. The evaluation of the study was based on a binary logistic regression model with the Wald test to analyses sociodemographic variables of marital status, gender, age, stage of academic study, and socioeconomic categories such as (students, the task, chance of practice, and outcomes anticipated). In addition, there is a relationship between the socioeconomic impact on student performance and all sociodemographic variables. Furthermore, the survey concentrates on indicating relationships between the variables of gender, age, and stage of academic study. There should be a test to analyses the links between both of them. At the 0.05 level of significance, Chi-square was employed to test the hypotheses. Social media is often utilized as a

criterion for deciding whether or not to include or exclude independent variables from a model.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i} \tag{1}$$

Based on the values of the independent variable predictors, binary logistic regression is used to forecast the likelihood of being a case. The odds are calculated by dividing the likelihood of a specific outcome being a case by the probability of it not being a case. The odds are calculated by dividing the likelihood of a specific outcome being a case by the likelihood of it not being a case. The odds are calculated by dividing the likelihood that a given outcome is a case by the probability that it is not. Binary logistic regression is a technique for describing data and explaining the relationship between one dependent binary variable and one or more independent variables at the ordinal, nominal, interval, or ratio level.

$$\ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right) = B_0 + B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + \dots + B_kX_k \tag{2}$$

In logistic regression, the Wald test is also utilized to determine whether a confirmed predictor variable X is significant. It is from the null hypothesis that the relevant coefficient of zero is rejected or unacceptable. In addition, the statistic shown is computed by dividing the coefficient by its the standard error. To think about the details with which to be measured as a measure. And also think about the details that are measured as a measure of the precision with which the regression coefficient is measured.

$$W = \frac{\hat{P}_1}{S_e(P_1)} \tag{3}$$

Furthermore, the odds ratio compares the probabilities of two events. The probability of events occurring divided by the probability of events not occurring is the probability of the event [24].

$$\text{Odds} = \frac{\pi}{\pi - 1} \tag{4}$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The distribution of the participants by gender is given in “Fig. 1,”.

Fig. 1: Gender of participants

When examining “Fig. 1,” the results of the analysis of participants by gender show that the majority of respondents

were female (67%), while 33% were male. Also, after the students' responses and analysis of the data, we found that the proportion of female students is higher than that of male students in Erbil universities. In the study, [23] found different results and show that, as the gender of participants shows, 50 percentage of the participants are male, as well as the rest 50 percentage are female.

The distribution of participants by marital statuses is given with “Fig. 2,”.

Fig. 2: Marital status of participants

When “Fig. 2,” is examined, it is seen that 95% of the participants are single and 5% of them are married according to marital status. Thus, it has been stated that single students have more time than married students and therefore have an advantage in education.

The academic study status of the participants is summarized in “Fig. 3,”.

Fig. 3: Academic study stage of participants

According to “Fig. 3,” 8% of the participants constitute the first stage, while 43% constitute the second stage. In addition, it was determined that 23% of the participants were in the third stage and lastly, the rate of those in the fourth grade was 26%.

The employment status of the fathers of the participants is given in “Fig. 1,”.

Fig. 4: Fathers working status of participants

When “Fig. 1,” is examined, 12% of the respondents' fathers were employed in the private sector, and 50% of the participants answered that their fathers worked in the public sector. As well as 24% of the participants said that their fathers were retired, while the remaining 14% said that their fathers could not work or were unemployed for various reasons.

The employment status of the mothers of the participants is given in “Fig. 5,”.

Fig. 5: Mothers working status of participants

When “Fig. 1,” is examined, 9% of the 230 participants stated that their mothers were employed in the public sector and 3% of them stated that their mothers were employed in the private sector. In addition, it can be said that 3% of the remaining participants' mothers are retired, and 85% of them are busy with housework and thus are unemployed.

The distribution of the participants' age is given in “Fig. 1,”.

Fig. 6: Age of participants

When “Fig. 1,” is examined, it is seen that the participants are divided into four different groups according to their age. Accordingly, it was determined that 32% of the respondents were among the ages of 18-20, 61% were among the ages of 20-24, 3% were among the ages of 24-26, and 4% were older than 26 years. This diversity of ages serves the purpose of the study. The results also show that the majority of college students who responded were between 20 and 24 years old. In this case, it can be said that the young people have very good opportunities to study in the city of Erbil, and therefore it has positive results on the performance as the young people are more lively and technologically educated.

The graph of the college expenditures of the participants is given in “Fig. 1,”. This figure, contains the results of the financial support of 230 students studying at Erbil universities.

Fig. 7: College expense of participants

When “Fig. 1,” is examined, 60% of the students say that their expenses are covered by their fathers, 27% by their guardian, 8% by their mothers and 5 by their own (other).

The distribution of the participants according to their income level is given in Table 1.

Income group (Iraqi dinar)	Frequency	Percentage
<500 000	60	26.1
500 000-750 000	61	26.5
750 000-1 000 000	59	25.7
>1 000 000	50	21.7
Total	230	100

Table 1: Classification of Participants by Income Group

When Table 1 is analyzed, it is seen that 26.1% of the participants have an income of less than 500 000 Iraqi Dinars (IQD) in terms of income. Also, 26.5% have an income between 500 000-750 000 IQD, 25.7% have an income between 750 000-1 000 000 IQD and the remaining 21.7% have an income of more than 1 000 000 IQD have been determined.

In order to determine the factors affecting the absenteeism to classes of the participants and thus their success, some descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation and frequency of each variable are given in Table 2.

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
You often miss to go to university every week	Agree	89	38.7	2.33	1.198
	Strongly agree	26	11.3		
	Disagree	65	28.3		
	Strongly disagree	50	21.7		
You always miss to go to university many days in a month	Agree	92	40.0	2.50	1.225
	Strongly agree	16	7.0		
	Disagree	70	30.4		
	Strongly disagree	52	22.6		
You are always absent from university many days a term	Agree	81	35.2	2.36	1.220
	Strongly agree	16	7.0		
	Disagree	71	30.9		
	Strongly disagree	62	27.0		

Table 2: Absenteeism of the Participants

As shown in the Table 2, 28.3% of students disagree, 38.7% agree, also 11.3% strongly agree and 21.7% strongly disagree about you often miss to go to university every week. You always miss to go to university many days in a month it was found that 30.4% of respondents disagree, as well as 22.6% strongly disagree, and 7.0% strongly agree, while 40.0% agree. Therefore, financial situation has an impact on the progress of students' education. The result

also you are always absent from university many days a term. According to the results, 35.2% of respondents agree, 30.9% disagree while 7.0% strongly agree and 27.0% strongly disagree.

The evaluation of factors encountered by students by participants and when asked about Financial in Table 3.

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Financial	Agree	150	65.2	1.87	1.229
	Strongly agree	0	0		
	Disagree	40	17.4		
	Strongly disagree	40	17.4		
Death of parents	Agree	46	20.0	3.09	2.15
	Strongly agree	12	5.2		
	Disagree	47	20.4		
	Strongly disagree	125	54.3		
Poverty	Agree	103	44.8	1.229	1.146
	Strongly agree	23	10.0		
	Disagree	71	30.9		
	Strongly disagree	62	27.0		

Table 3: Factors Encountered by Students

As indicated in Table 3, about finance 65.2% of the responding students agreed, while this percentage decreased to 17.4% and 17.4% participating to disagree and strongly disagree, respectively. Concerning the death of parents, we have asked the respondents and found that 20.4% of the participants selected disagree, while this increased to 54.3% strongly disagree, as well as the percentage of participants who agree at 20.0% and 5.2%

strongly agree. On the other hand, when asked about poverty, the respondents, the highest percentage 44.8% agreed with decreased to 30.9% disagree, as well as 14.3% strongly disagree and 10.0% strongly agree.

The reasons for fuel consumption for cooking are explained in Table 4.

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
You always use Gas	Agree	135	58.7	1.76	1.016
	Strongly agree	34	14.8		
	Disagree	43	18.7		
	Strongly disagree	18	7.8		
You always use Electricity	Agree	126	54.8	1.85	1.027
	Strongly agree	28	12.2		
	Disagree	61	26.5		
	Strongly disagree	15	8.5		
You always use Firewood	Agree	39	17.0	2.95	0.992
	Strongly agree	2	0.9		
	Disagree	121	52.6		
	Strongly disagree	68	29.6		

Table 4: Using of Fuel to Cook

According to the result of the Table 4, 18.2% the participants disagree and increased to 59.2% agree on they do not have enough you always use gas. This is how they answered about always using electricity to cook 26.5% disagree as well as 54.8% agree, while 12.2% strongly agree and 8.5% disagree. Also, 26.6% of the participants selected disagreed with being used to having food outside, while this increased to 37.9% agreeing. In addition, they

always used wood for cooking. When the participants were asked about it, they responded with 52.6% disagreeing and 0.9% strongly agreeing.

To identify the factors that influence the use source of water for home, we also used statistics for descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation and frequency of each variable listed in Table 5.

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
you are using legitimate water	Agree	137	59.6	1.83	1.126
	Strongly agree	26	11.3		
	Disagree	36	15.7		
	Strongly disagree	31	13.5		
you fetch water from the well	Agree	105	45.7	2.13	1.151
	Strongly agree	25	10.9		
	Disagree	66	28.7		
	Strongly disagree	34	14.8		
you fetch water from the River	Agree	44	19.1	2.93	1.071
	Strongly agree	8	3.5		
	Disagree	98	42.6		
	Strongly disagree	80	34.8		

Table 5: Use Source of Water for Home

Furthermore, those who used water projects responded that according to Table 5, 59.6% were agreed, as well as 11.3% were strongly agreed, 15.7% disagreed, and 13.5% were very strongly disagreed. The output of the result reflected that 14.8% of you fetch water from the well disagree and increased 45.7% agreed they used well water.

Also, you fetch water from the River disagreed 33.4% of the participants while this decreased to 3.5% of strongly agree.

The Reasons for students dropping out of university, the participating students answered as follows in Table 6.

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Helping in the house	Agree	142	61.7	1.66	0.966
	Strongly agree	41	17.8		
	Disagree	30	13.0		
	Strongly disagree	17	7.4		
Caring for younger siblings	Agree	118	51.3	1.88	1.073
	Strongly agree	50	21.7		
	Disagree	33	14.3		
	Strongly disagree	29	12.6		
Because there is no employment	Agree	70	30.4	2.53	1.170
	Strongly agree	27	11.7		
	Disagree	75	32.6		
	Strongly disagree	58	25.2		
Lack of interest in study	Agree	51	22.2	2.73	1.103

Variable		Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
	Strongly agree	25	10.9		
	Disagree	88	38.3		
	Strongly disagree	51	22.2		

Table 6: Reasons for Dropout

Table 6. indicated that 7.4 percentage of the participants answering strongly disagree and the rate increased to 61.7 percentage agree with helping in their house. Participants responded to their Caring for younger siblings 30.4% disagree and 12.6% strongly agree. As well as 32.6% of the participants selected disagree because there is no employment while this decreased to 30.4% agree. Moreover, 22.2% of the lack of interest in study have chosen agree and increased to 38.3% respondent disagreed about Lack of interest in study.

A. Relationship Between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and the Effect Socio-Economy on Performance Student

The relationship between the socio-demographic factor and the socioeconomic effect on university students' performance is determined using the chi-square (χ^2) test in Table 7. In addition, the Chi-square (χ^2) test was utilized for acquisition the relationship among categorical variables. According to the study, there is a significant relationship among socioeconomic and sociodemographic factors.

Factor		Percentage	χ^2	p Value
Gender	Male	33.5%	24.905	0.000
	Female	66.5%		
Age group	18-20 years	32.2%	35.556	0.000
	20-24 years	61.3%		
	24-26 years	2.6%		
	Above 26 years	3.9%		
Marital status	Single	95.2%	7.653	0.000
	Married	4.8%		
Academic study stage	First stage	7.8%	31.055	0.000
	Second stage	43%		
	Third stage	23.5%		
	Forth stage	25.7%		
Father employment status	Employed in public sector	50.4%	62.113	0.000
	Employed in private sector	11.7%		
	Unemployed	14.3%		
	Retired	23.5%		
Mother employment status	Employed in public sector	8.7%	18.947	0.000
	Employed in private sector	3%		
	Unemployed	85.2%		
	Retired	3%		
Parents average monthly income	Less than 500000 IQ	26.1%	25.817	0.000
	500000IQ – 750000 IQ	26.5%		
	750000IQ – 1000000 IQ	25.7%		
	More than 1000000	21.7%		

Table 6: Relationship between Demographic Characteristics and the Effect Socioeconomic on Performance Student

Table 7 indicates a statistically significant relationship between gender and socio demographic factor such as gender and socioeconomic.

According to the result the relationship among gender and 'the effect socio economic on performance student' is statistically significant ($\chi^2=24.905$; $p:0.000$). According to the results, 33.5% of students were male and female regarding gender, and that increased to 66.5%. There is a statistically significant relationship among "age group" and "the effect of socioeconomic factors on student performance ($\chi^2=35.556$; $p:0.000$). According to the results show that those aged 24 to 26 responded with 2.6%, and those aged 20 to 24 had the highest proportion of students, rising to 61.3%. While there was a statistically significant coefficient relationship among "marital status" and the effect socioeconomic on students' performance and other independent variables such as marital status ($\chi^2=7.653$;

$p:0.000$). Moreover, the results show that those who are single responded with 95.2% and those who are married were the least percentage of students 4.8%.

Furthermore, the results we obtained explain that the relationship between the academic study stage and the impact of socioeconomic on students' performance is statistically significant ($\chi^2=13.055$; $p=0.000$). In addition, about 43% of the students chose the second stage, and it dropped to 7.8% the first stage in the academic stage. Furthermore, the findings showed that the relationship between, employment status father and the effect of socioeconomic on students' performance ($\chi^2=62.113$; $p=0.000$) is significant. In addition, about 50.4% of respondents worked in various public sectors and the rest worked in the private sector, which decreased to 11.7% working in the private sector. According to the results of the study [25], the results vary, showing that the most

common occupation of fathers in the district was agriculture (50%); most of the students reported that their fathers and mothers were farmers. In an identical study, [26] the results varied, showing the occupations of the students' fathers. Most of the students who responded said their fathers worked in the private sector 52.7%. As well, the proportion of fathers working in the public sector was 38.2%.

Also, the relationship among mother employment status and “socioeconomic effect on student performance ($\chi^2=18.947$; $p:0.000$). The output show that 85.2% of the participants chose unemployment when their mothers did not work, and the percentage of students who said their mothers were retired decreased to 3%. The results indicate the study [25], in addition to the difference in outcomes, that a large number of mothers were farmers (69%) while (31%) were businesswomen. Other occupations made up a small percentage. Additionally, there is a statistically significant relationship between parents' average monthly income and socioeconomic impact on university students' performance ($\chi^2=25.817$; $p:0.000$). Most respondents,

26.5%, responded that their monthly salary was between 500,000 IQ – 750,000 IQ. Some respondents responded that the figure dropped to 21.7%, whose monthly salary was more than 1,000,000 IQ. On the other hand, according to [27], the result indicates differently than the parents' income has no significant coefficient relationship to their students learning accomplishment. According to the study [26], the results are different Less than 2,000 Nakfa 50.9%.

B. Relationship Between Students Characteristics and the Effect Socio-Economy on Performance Student

The relationship between the characteristics of university students in Erbil is shown in Table 8, which indicates a statistically significant coefficient relationship among the impact socioeconomic on performance student' and (pays college expenses, personal laptop, personal mobile, comfortable chair for study at home, spread room for study at home, homework, visit your college, required at college, academic achievement, environment, satisfied in the performance of university institution and perform in academic).

Factor		Percentage	χ^2	p Value
Who pays college expenses	Father	60%	57.701	0.000
	Mother	8.3%		
	Guardian	27%		
	Other	4.8%		
Do you have personal laptop	Yes	43%	21.84	0.000
	No	57%		
Do you have personal mobile	Yes	97%	4.727	0.028
	No	3%		
Do you have comfortable chair for study at home	Yes	31.3%	22.984	0.000
	No	68.8%		
Do you have a separate room for study at home	Yes	51.3%	28.209	0.000
	No	48.7%		
Do you parents ensure that you do your homework	Yes	86.5%	7.072	0.000
	No	13.5%		
To what extent your parents visit your college to inquire about your progress	Always	72.6%	27.609	0.000
	Sometime	24.3%		
	Never	3%		
Do your parents buy you extra personal material required at college	Yes	87.4%	7.028	0.008
	No	12.6%		
Goal of academic achievement	Skills	68.3%	41.712	0.000
	Social	20.9%		
	Financial	3.5%		
	Other	7.4%		

Table 7: Relationship between Social Characteristics and the Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement of University Students

Moreover, the result illustrated a significant relationship among how pays college expenses has a positive and significant impact on the effect socioeconomic on performance student' ($\chi^2=57.701$, $p:0.000$). According to the result that shown 4.8% of the participants chose other concerning pays college expenses and increased to 60% father. There is a significant relationship can be observed between Do you have personal laptop and the effect socioeconomic on performance student ($\chi^2=21.84$; $p:0.000$) is significant. In addition, a large number of participants who have a personal laptop said no

(57%), and 43% said yes, we have our own laptop. As found in the results, the relationship between Do you have personal mobile the effect socioeconomic on performance student ($\chi^2=4.727$; $p:0.028$). The highest percentage of respondents (97%) said yes to responsibility, and only 3% of respondents said no to having a personal mobile phone.

In addition, the result showed that there is a statistically significant relationship among do you have comfortable chair for study at home and the effect socioeconomic on student performance ($\chi^2=22.984$; $p:0.000$). On the other hand, you have a seat for home

study, and the outcome represent that a total of 68.8% of participants answered yes and 31.3% of respondents said no. Furthermore, the results represented that the relationship among Do you have spread room for study at home and the effect socioeconomic on performance student ($\chi^2=28.209$; $p:0.000$) is significant. Additionally, about 51.3% of the students chose yes about having separate rooms for home study, and no to 48.7% about not having separate rooms for home study. The result of statistically significant relationship between Do you parents ensure that you do your homework and the effect socio economic on performance student ($\chi^2=7.022$; $p:0.000$). The outcome indicates that 13.5% of participants chose no concerning making sure parents do their homework, and that number increased to 86.5% who chose yes about making sure students do their homework.

In addition, the relationship between to what extent your parents visit your college to inquire about your progress and the effect socio economic on performance student is statistically significant coefficient ($\chi^2=27.609$; $p:0.000$). Moreover, the result, the percentage of students who said their parents never visit college to ask about their

progress rose to 72.6 percent. Based on the significant relationship between do your parents buy you extra personal material required at college and the effect socio economic on performance student ($\chi^2=7.028$; $p:0.008$). According to the result the show that the students who said no were 12.6%, and the respondents who chose yes about having parents buy them additional personal materials needed in college rose to 87.4%. On the other hand, the result of the statistically significant coefficient the relationship between goal of academic achievement and the effect socio economic on performance student ($\chi^2=41.712$; $p:0.000$) is a statistically significant coefficient. In addition, While the students who responded that they are proficient in academic achievement goals (68.3%) also dropped to 3.5% of students who said that money helps them to achieve challenges academically.

C. Results binary Logistic Regression

Descriptions of the variables utilized in the model are given in Table 9. In binary Logistic Model, continuous variables Do you have all the necessary stationery for learning.

Variable	Definition	Definition of Variable	Mean	SD
Age	Age of respondents	Less than 750000	0.07	0.247
		More than 750000		
Gender	Gender of respondents	0: Female	0.33	0.473
		1: Male		
Academic study stage	Academic study stage	0: first stage, secondary stage	0.49	0.501
		1: third Stage, fourth stage		
Parents average monthly income	Monthly income of respondents	Dinars	0.47	0.500
Do you have all the necessary stationery for learning	Necessary stationery for learning of respondents	0: No	1.20	0.404
		1: Yes		
Financial	Financial of respondents	0: Disagree	0.65	0.477
		1: Agree		
You always use Firewood	Always use Firewood of respondents	0: Disagree	0.18	0.384
		1: Agree		
Because there is no employment	No employment of respondents	0: Disagree	0.42	0.495
		1: Agree		

Table 8: Descriptive the Statistics of the Variables in the Binary Logistic Model

As indicated by examining the impact socioeconomic on performance student, the understudy's twofold logit model was utilized. Table 10 demonstrates illustrative insights into factors in the model.

Variable	Coefficients	Std. Error	Wald test	p-values	Odds Ratio
Age	-6.133	1.526	16.157	0.000	0.002
Gender	1.278	0.478	7.163	0.007	3.590
Academic study stage	-2.075	0.709	8.572	0.003	0.126
Monthly income	1.980	0.821	5.820	0.016	7.244
Necessary stationery for learning	4.196	1.446	8.424	0.004	66.402
Financial	-2.578	0.537	23.053	0.000	0.076
Always using Firewood	1.310	0.486	7.274	0.007	3.705
No employment	0.567	0.651	0.759	0.384	1.763
Constant	3.689	1.930	3.652	0.056	40.006
-2 log likelihood	208.830				

Variable	Coefficients	Std. Error	Wald test	p-values	Odds Ratio
Nagelkerke			0.477		
χ^2			99.927		
p value			0.000		

Table 9: Binary Logit Model for the Impact Socioeconomic on Performance Student

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

Also, the Nagelkerke R² variation, which ambit from 0 to 1, is a more variable measure of the association among variables.

For our situation, it is 0.477, demonstrating a somewhat solid relationship among the indicators and the expectations in Table 10. In the event that the HL integrity of fit test measurement is higher than 0.05, as we need well-adequate models, we neglect to dismiss the invalid speculation that there is no distinction among noticed and anticipated qualities, suggesting that the model's gauge fits the information at a satisfactory level.

In addition, to the results of binary logistic regression; there were a statistically significant coefficient relationship among the effect socioeconomic on performance student and Visibility with Age, Gender, Academic study stage, Monthly income of respondents, do you have all the necessary stationery for learning, financial and you always use firewood, but there is no employment, no relationship and significant. Furthermore, that statistically significant coefficient indicates that age negatively influences the socioeconomic impact on student performance. According to the result it was determined that the odds ratio of visibility with age is statistically significant coefficient for socioeconomic effect on student performance (0.002). Moreover, the finding of statistically significant coefficient showed that the gender has a positive impacted on the effect socioeconomic on performance student. According to the result shown that the odds ratio of the gender for the effect socioeconomic on performance student (3.590) times more likely to involve in socioeconomic on performance student.

According to the result of the statistically significant represented that academic study stage has a negative effect on the effect socioeconomic on performance student. Furthermore, the output showed that the odds ratio of academic study stage for the economic effects on performance on performance students (0.126) times less likely to involve in socioeconomic on performance students. Moreover, for the outcome, monthly income had a positive impact on the socioeconomic impact on student performance because of a statistically significant coefficient. The outcomes showed the odd ratio of monthly income to socioeconomic status (7.244) is more likely to contribute to on students' performance. In addition to the results of the survey of [12], found the same results, showing that as, parents' income has strong and statistically significant relationship to learning achievement of their children. In a similar study, [26], the results were different, the results were that there was no statistically significant coefficient and relationship between the effect of

socioeconomic on students' performance and parents average monthly income chi square: 0.181; p:0.671. Based on statistically significant coefficients, stationery essential for student learning has a significant positive effect of socioeconomic status on university students' performance. In addition, the results showed that the probability of writing materials needed for learning was 66.402.

In addition, the significant statistics regarding finances appear to had a negative impact on the impact of socioeconomics on university students' performance. The outcomes showed that the odds ratio of the socioeconomic effect on student performance was 0.076. In addition, the result of the statistically significant coefficient represented that always using firewood has a positive effect on the socioeconomic effect on student performance. Furthermore, the result showed that the odds ratio of always using firewood (3.705) is times less likely to have a socioeconomic effect on student performance.

V. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to investigate the effects of socioeconomic status of university students in the city of Erbil on their success. The sample was randomly selected from university students in the city of Erbil. Questionnaire was used as data collection tool. In addition, the statistical analysis was performed for categorical variables to determine percentages and frequencies. Also, Chi-square test value was taken into account to find the relationship between categorical variables.

Eight variables were included in the Logit model due to age, gender, academic status, average monthly income of parents, stationery required for education, financial situation, always using Firewood, and lack of employment. According to the significance levels observed for the logistic regression coefficients, it can be said that the remaining seven of these eight variables, excluding unemployment, have statistically significant effects on the socioeconomic status of the students. As can be understood from the outcomes obtained, it is shown that age has a negative effect on the socioeconomic level that affects student performance. Age is clearly an important factor with odds ratio of 0.002 for socioeconomic impact on student performance. In addition to age, it is seen that the financial status and academic study stages, respectively, negatively and significantly affect the socioeconomic performance of the students. Odds ratio values of these two variables were obtained as 0.076 and 0.126, respectively. On the other hand, it was determined that the variables of necessary stationery materials for learning, monthly income, always using firewood and gender respectively,

have positive and significant effects on the socioeconomic performance of the students. The odds ratio values for these four variables, which positively affect student performance, were obtained as 66,402, 7.244, 3.705 and 3.705, respectively.

It is recommended to be very careful in researches in this field, because a good education that will increase the performance of students is effective in the formation of a modern and progressive society. Thus, it can be said that parents have a great influence on the academic performance of students. In addition, the state should help families, especially poor families, so that students can continue their education. In order to improve individual learning outcomes in education, the government should increase educational opportunities, and a system suitable for the conditions of the society and students should be preferred. If it is accepted that the best work to be left to future generations is an educated and conscious society, Families should invest in their children's education and in this context, provide an environment where they can study, supervise them and meet all their needs.

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